

Co- development of HARDOCS: An Open Source Tool to make FAIR data easy to adopt in hardware and product design

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Introduction

The current work reports on a 6 month long co-creation activity funded by the EOSC Secretariat to explore how FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data can be adopted and embedded in a tool to enable commonly understood documentation processes in the context of hardware and product design.

In this work we define *FAIR by design* as a notion to articulate FAIR principles in the context of tools, frameworks and systems design. An example of exercising this *FAIR by design* idea could be that users can easily specify what metadata standard they want to work with in a specific project in their daily workflow, or easily package and publish datasets, source files and resources. Another example could be, creating easy documentation that explains and gives context to source files like code, images, bills of materials etc. Being able to version documents in very simple ways, as well as relating them to other projects and resources are other examples that could articulate this principle of *FAIR by design* in our view.

Background and motivation

Documentation processes are essential to make innovation and science more findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). To give an illustrative example, there have been many groups around the world developing hardware designs of equipment, as a response to address the COVID-19 crisis, and the subsequent shortage of accessories and medical equipment such as ventilators. A major challenge associated with this collective intent to generate solutions around the world was the difficulty to find, assess and reuse the solutions generated, in contrast with software, where there are standard tools and practices widely adopted and understood.

Managing data and documentation in domains such as hardware and product design can be complex. How can we implement FAIR principles in the documentation and publishing of hardware designs? In order to address some of the challenges associated with these documentation processes, we conducted a set of activities with software developers and end users focused on improving current experiences of hardware design documentation.

Even though there are many tools to document and publish projects in various ways and formats (often intended for software development), they require a certain level of expertise, software culture and familiarity with certain tools. Markdown, for instance, is a widely used format to document projects and generate beautiful static documentation websites, but it is not very suitable when users want to edit images inside of documents and see those images while writing their texts. Setting up static websites to publish documentation also requires users to use typed commands on a terminal, which could be an obstacle in certain disciplines where web

technologies, programming and git version control are not widely adopted or required. Examples of these disciplines could be mechanical engineering, industrial design or architecture. Having a centralized and also local registry of documentation projects could make the experience more natural and organic.

From our point of view, the challenges we try to address don't rely on a lack of metadata standards, availability of specific tools or initiatives. We think the challenge is in addressing those specific aspects of hardware design objects and documents that shape and constrain the practices and workflows of documentation. The main motivation behind this co-creation activity has been to articulate some opportunities and design ideas to address some of these documentation processes specific to hardware design.

The subsequent work resulted in a set of design premises, a software architecture design to address these design premises, and a desktop application that facilitates the generation and editing of documents in the context of hardware design. We hope that this work provides useful steps towards making documentation *FAIR by design* in the context of hardware.

Methodology

From its inception this co-creation has been framed as a research and feasibility demonstration effort. It has been guided by continuous exchange, and driven by a hands-on development approach. Rather than being sequential, it has been mostly composed of regular feedback loops of conceptualization, development and evaluation; a continuous dialogue between two technical experts and two domain experts, guided by Domain Driven Design(DDD) tools, such as event storming [1], and Agile software development practices [2].

In the context of DDD we refer to the technical expertise role, as one focused on researching technical requirements, considerations and constraints to address a particular set of domain related needs. A technical expert articulates software architecture design based on the domain logic and available solutions. This role identifies technical challenges and explores the possibilities towards an appropriate software architecture. Domain experts provide context to technical experts including domain vocabulary, notions, concepts as well as tasks and workflows they follow in their common practices. These common domain specific practices are often known as the "business domain" in the software world. In this project, domain experts were coming from disciplines such as mechanical engineering, electronic engineering, industrial design (hardware related disciplines).

The following are the specific activities that took place during the co-creation process:

De-briefing the assignment with technical experts.

The initial description of the assignment, as well as a set of documents describing the needs for HARDOCS, were used as a basis to define the scope of the project and the domain context.

Collecting use cases from the hardware documentation process for a specific set of projects focused on covid 19 solutions.

Substantial information, inspiration and learnings were gathered from the CombatCovid [3] documentation processes. It is important to mention that CombatCovid has also been an open source project co-developed by this team prior to starting hardocs. Combatcovid works on top of github API(Application Programming Interface) and uses github capabilities as a basis to deliver a better experience for presenting and finding content, it is globally capable and delivers instant search for users. Nevertheless the specific process of documenting and publishing designs was rather complex in github for the users. This was due to the fact that users were not familiar with

software practices of version control with git. This experience allowed us to spot limitations related to the creation, publishing, collaboration and sharing of hardware projects using common tools like markdown, git repositories and github. We explored this tool and workflow with 33 participants and created about 20 documentation projects. This information and feedback was used as a basis to inform the development of Hardocs.

Specifying requirements, core features and exploring possible solutions.

This part included the development of visual mockups, models and evaluating technology possibilities. It also involved verifying the promising technologies to have more insight on what was feasible to implement and address during this co-creation. Our app is entirely based on available open source tools and components. This allowed us to quickly explore the possibilities, challenges and customizations needed to articulate the design vision and implement it.

Fig.1 Example of visual mockup produced in early stages of the co-creation activity.

Fig.2. Initial model of software scoping for the first phase based on design premises and subsequent requirements

Software and open source development.

The software development work has been done in an agile style by having weekly meetings to check progress and steer design and development intents. The amount of success in adapting and integrating available open source solutions allowed us to rapidly prototype and gain in research throughout progress on the implementation. The project has been structured in discrete and therefore approachable areas and modules.

Co-creation results

Design premises

Premises used as guidelines included a general criterion and also a “style” that we wanted Hardocs to reflect in its implementation. This style was heavily inspired by the experiences we had when providing the [Combatcovid](#) web application on top of github and a cloud ‘habitat’, to document hardware designs. These premises also take ideas from [git](#), and from widely used editors like [vscode](#) in their approaches. The following list briefly presents them:

- Enable FAIR principles by design
- Support local and offline first workflows
- Support the use of standards for different knowledge domains
- Easy metadata editing in local environments
- Private first collaboration
- Integrate with the cloud using a hybrid approach
- Architect for a fully global capability

You can find more explanation of each premise [in the documentation website](#) [4].

Architectural design

The architecture specifies how the app will work in the cloud in combination with the desktop app. A basis of strongly defensible security has been a fundamental principle throughout the design and specifics of developed implementation for this architecture. In Fig. 3, you can observe that all operations center around a basic structure in the database and at all levels, which is called the “Hardocs object”. The “Hardocs object” is a data tree composed of useful elements including summary documents, with their images and metadata. You can read more about the [architecture](#) on the HARDOCS website [9] with the detailed explanation of the architectural design.

Fig.3 Hardocs current architecture and data structure, implementing local-offline with secure private first, then public on decision to publish as premises

Verified technical options in app-basis-framework

The app-basis-framework is a set of useful results and partial verifications which allowed us to learn from [demonstrator models](#) [5]. These models represent know-how captured in partial implementation examples that were later used as a knowledge basis to develop the desktop

app, the cloud service as well as a service API. Examples of these models include the testing of pouchdb, html editors, the integration of custom developed libraries, exporting to multiple formats using pandoc, among other important tests. We chose to go fully with web technologies and a hybrid app approach powered by [Electronjs](#) [6], which is an enabler to operate across several platforms and implement an application that combines web technologies and native desktop technologies. Fig.4 shows a screenshot view of how the app-basis-framework was used to explore solutions.

Fig.4 Screenshot of app-basis framework integrating key technologies including Vuejs, PouchDB for local database and Electron as basis framework.

Developed modules (separate repositories) to handle core application requests

The application uses several services with operations that we have developed, which are modularized to facilitate maintenance and distributed software development. See our [\(list of repositories in this link and the bibliography \[7\]\)](#)

Implemented and released the open source Hardocs desktop app [8]

The app is fully open source and also based on open source libraries like vuejs, ckeditor and electron. This means that the subsequent documentation enables other potential collaborators to participate in the development of the application. Details of the [desktop app](#) can be found on the Hardocs website and the provided git repository [8].

Following in Fig. 5 is a view of some features in the desktop app, including a central portion of its intended ability, to provide simple writing and composing of illustrated Project Summary Documents, which in full implementation, Hardocs will allow to be discovered and shared.

Fig 5. Application view showing key editing features like adding images and making tables for bills of materials. As it can be seen the documents also live in the file system specified by the user. This facilitates the data to persist, while living in close proximity to more elaborate digital objects which may be shared through the Design Project's own typical website, such as CAD models or csv files.

Delivered project documentation and code base documentation

An important deliverable of this activity is the extensive documentation of different aspects of the project that include project management documents like issue tracking on github, repository documentation, co-creation documentation and a website that allows readers to provide feedback interactively. This documentation package can be accessed via this static website available at [Hardocs website](#).

Follow-up

The fact that CombatCovid preceded this work was key to the success of this project. CombatCovid, like Hardocs, is open source. This application was fully participative and open from its start, which allowed the team members to meet and learn how to work together, motivated to do something about the covid 19 crisis at the start of 2020. This experience also allowed the team to gain insights on the specific domain we were designing for, hardware design. Therefore you can consider this project(Hardocs) as part of a continuous process preceded and heavily influenced by the experience of CombatCovid.

Accomplishments of this co-creation

Reaching a scalable and feasible architecture design is a major result of these co-creation. This aspect of the work is the synthesis of the needs and desires expressed in actual implementations and feasible technical solutions. Even though architectural principles are not always directly visible to the end user, they are the pillars that make possible appropriate user experiences.

Concrete accomplishments include:

- Designing on the basis of CombatCovid learnings. This approach gave us solid insights on what to consider in the design process of Hardocs design.
- Investigated, chose, and integrated a set of libraries, services, and solutions to use in the cloud and in the main application, cooperatively attuning the architecture according to abilities discovered and verified through our development period.
- Created a working base model of the Habitat cloud services, which includes strong security, high-capacity front end, the replicable document database, and the Habitat protocol api to operate the current set of functions, live and exercised on the internet.
- Delivered an application that articulates many of the desktop design premises proposed. The tool can be used to document projects easily. It exports the documents into html which allows users to easily publish them and reuse them in the context of the web.
- Provided a Hardocs Framework application which was used to develop a set of client side api protocols for database, Electron platform services, and the Habitat cloud.
- Enabled a powerful editor library with fresh development which makes possible the Desktop app's intention for template-accelerated standards-based composition of the metadata portion of Hardocs projects. This is a work in progress, while its framework also shows promise towards creation of the templates themselves.
- Provided ability for Hardocs to have its full project content present also as files, which can live side-by-side with other digital assets (CAD models, sheets, images), aiding backup and expanded uses.

Limitations of HARDOCS current status

- Feasibility of further functionalities have been verified, but not integrated in the application, while others have been partially integrated but not to a point where they can be used reliably. One important case is the metadata editing capabilities. This feature would allow users to specify per project in which metadata standard they would like to document their project.
- Usability tests of the final product were substantially limited compared to what was originally expected. This is mainly because the application was still being developed, and therefore was not ready to be released to a wider audience.
- Promised documented hardware designs of covid19 related hardware using hardocs were not delivered, nevertheless these examples can be found in the combatcovid website, which shows some of the capabilities and ideas behind hardocs architected models.
- The cloud services models have been developed through several levels including high-grade identity-based security and location/project private facilities, including replicable database and operational client api protocols, while not yet in the separate publishing-capable layer of the cloud, which would begin to open the actual co-creation features of the Hardocs architecture.
- The current cloud result is demonstrable by a framework dashboard, but not yet integrated into the app, so that at present it operates locally.
- As the architecture was composed to be capable as a full-service, widely available system, there are many features which while kept well in awareness, have not been included. These features are in easily imagined areas such as robust and flexible search, and publicly offerable APIs.

As a simple note for the desktop portion itself, at this stage:

- The installation should be able to be lighter than it is now, about 70 MB at the moment.
- The application needs further unit test coverage in order to be more robust and reliable.

Conclusions

At the start of this co-creation activity it was originally proposed to deliver a working product that would integrate cloud features and desktop application features, we also aimed to have substantial usability feedback based on the delivered product within the scope of this 6 month project. Nevertheless, conducting a co-creative process of researching, designing and discussing, was in permanent tension with the process of releasing software that works reliably (The first process is mostly focused on experimenting, investigating and exploring, on efficiency and productivity). We learned that the scope was too ambitious from a technical standpoint for 6 months.

The project was progressively re-scoped through iterations, prioritizing essential features and work areas to create a solid foundation for future developments. Throughout our process the true extent of a fully implemented, globally capable system became clearer and more feasible. At the same time, we learned that more dedicated time and resources are required to achieve a robust, adoptable and mature solution. Therefore we recommend continuing at least another round of co-creation and refinement in this same methodological format, where more focus is put on getting feedback from users. This follow-on round could progressively add features

towards making the cloud service and data management abilities more visible and usable, as planned in the architectural design.

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